

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PREVENTION OF EMOTIONAL BURNOUT OF TEACHERS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Emotional burnout syndrome is a condition manifested by psycho-emotional, mental and physical exhaustion, which leads to the paralysis of our forces and feelings and is accompanied by a loss of joy and satisfaction in life in response to long-term exposure to stressful and psycho-traumatic factors.

Analysis of the problem of "emotional burnout", which is a response to chronic emotional stress, confirms its destructive effect on the professional activity and personality of a medical university teacher. Burnout intensifies in conditions of distance learning and quarantine restrictions. The teaching activity of scientific and pedagogical workers of universities requires constant self-development, improvement of professional knowledge, abilities and skills, somatic and mental health, which are limited in quarantine conditions. Timely prevention of a teacher's professional deformation and stabilization of his psycho-emotional state will prevent the occurrence of emotional burnout and contribute to the quality performance of his professional duties. The reason for the development of emotional burnout at work is "chronic fatigue", caused by a discrepancy between the personality and the demands placed on it. Constant stresses associated, first of all, with the peculiarities of professional activity, namely: information overload, extreme situations, intensive level of communication, high degree of responsibility - contribute to the development of the syndrome of "emotional burnout" in teachers of higher education and are accompanied by disorders of psychosomatic and of a somatopsychic nature. The lack of conditions for relieving psychological fatigue and insufficient competence in matters of preserving and strengthening professional health deepen the problems arising in this situation among teachers. Recommendations for the prevention of emotional burnout of medical university teachers should include: optimization of the work and rest regime; reasonable load distribution; reduction of conflict at work; psychological relief; manifestation of self-care; a careful attitude to work planning in the conditions of "quarantine" education, a balanced approach to the amount of independent tasks for students and the most important thing in this situation - work should be a joy.

That is why the study of the peculiarities of development and ways of prevention requires a systematic approach, the use of various methods, as well as the development of modern technologies to preserve psychological health among teachers of higher educational institutions and is an urgent issue today.

Keywords: emotional burnout, depersonalization, welcome instability, reduction of professional achievements, aromatherapy.

Specific factors of professional activity in higher education, which negatively affect the professional and personal development of university teachers, are the following: multifunctionality of professional activity; large amount of work; the intensity of communicative interaction in the "person-to-person" sphere; heterogeneity of the student audience in terms of intellectual and socio-cultural features, level of responsibility, general education, direction of educational and professional motivation, etc. According to the conclusions of researchers in the field of social psychology, occupational health psychology, and work psychology, on the one hand, work contributes to the personal and professional development of a specialist, and on the other hand, it can negatively affect him. Therefore, preventing the impact of negative factors related to professional activity is an important task of maintaining the professional's ability to work. Among these, a negative phenomenon in professional activity is professional burnout (emotional exhaustion). Therefore, one of the tasks of training in a higher educational institution is

the formation of psychophysical stability and self-organizational competence of the future specialist, thanks to which he is able to choose the appropriate style of behavior and organization of activities in order to prevent the negative influence of the profession [1, 8].

In the scientific literature, a number of terms are used to denote the phenomenon of burnout: emotional burnout, emotional exhaustion, professional burnout, professional exhaustion. N. Konovchuk notes that the phenomenon of emotional burnout (exhaustion) is broader and includes the concept of "professional burnout", the main cause of which he identifies as an organizational factor (working conditions, working atmosphere, relations with superiors and colleagues, etc.) [3].

Professional burnout of a higher school teacher can be caused by objective and subjective factors [18].

The objective factors are the following [12]:

- socio-economic transformations in Ukraine that affect the material stability of society members, psychological state and professional well-being;

- risk of job loss due to lack of funds, associated with low (absent) funding and insufficient number of applicants during the admissions campaign;

- failure to provide the employee with a full working rate if he wishes to work fully and qualitatively;

- overloading the teacher with work tasks in the absence of encouragement and appropriate remuneration, etc.

Subjective factors include the following:

- insufficient motivation or unformed value attitude to professional activity;

- some personal characteristics: anxiety, introversion, perfectionism, workaholicism, presenteeism, etc.;

- inadequacy of professional expectations, self-esteem, etc.

There are the following definitions of burnout syndrome [20]:

- a mechanism of psychological protection developed by the individual in the form of complete or partial exclusion of emotions in response to some psycho-traumatic actions, an acquired stereotype of emotional, mostly professional behavior. Burnout is partly a functional stereotype, as it allows a person to dose and economically spend energy resources. At the same time, its dysfunctional consequences may arise, when burnout negatively affects professional activity (V.V. Boyko);

- the process of gradual loss of emotional, cognitive and physical energy, manifested in symptoms of emotional and mental exhaustion, physical fatigue, personal detachment and decreased satisfaction from the work performed (P. Sidorov);

- an appropriate reaction to long-term professional stresses of interpersonal communication, which contains three components: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduction of personal achievements (S. Maslach and S. Jackson) [6];

- physical, emotional or motivational exhaustion, characterized by a decrease in work productivity, fatigue, insomnia, increased susceptibility to somatic diseases, as well as the use of alcohol or other psychoactive substances for the purpose of obtaining temporary relief, which tends to the development of physiological dependence.

Symptoms of emotional burnout syndrome are as follows (K. Maslakh) [6]:

- 1) emotional exhaustion: the employee develops chronic fatigue, mood deteriorates (sometimes even just at the mention of work), sleep disturbances, diffuse physical ailments, susceptibility to diseases;

- 2) depersonalization/dehumanization – a cynical attitude towards work and its objects (subjects): negative attitude towards colleagues and those who need help, feelings of guilt, the employee often chooses formal functioning and avoids workloads at all costs;

- 3) reduction of professional achievements - employees feel incompetent and aware of failure in their professional field; the employee suffers from a lack of recognition, success, loss of control over the situation, feels unsolicited and excessive demands on himself;

- 4) welcome instability (H.Sonnek, 1994): depression, depressed mood, excitability, feeling of oppression towards oneself, anxiety, restlessness, feeling of hopelessness, irritability.

There are four groups of workers who are most susceptible to professional burnout [7]:

- 1) introverts, whose individual and psychological characteristics do not agree with the professional requirements of communicative professions. They do not have an excess of vital energy, are modest, shy, prone to introversion and concentration on the subject of professional activity, which causes emotional discomfort;

- 2) employees who experience a constant internal conflict related to work;

- 3) women who experience an internal contradiction between work and family, as well as pressure due to the need to constantly prove their professional capabilities in conditions of fierce competition with men;

- 4) specialists whose professional activity takes place in conditions of acute instability and chronic fear of job loss, as well as employees who occupy the position of external consultants on the labor market, forced to find clients on their own.

In the psychological and pedagogical scientific literature, there are three approaches to explaining the emergence of the syndrome of professional burnout [9]:

- 1) individual-psychological: discrepancy between high expectations of individuals regarding work and reality;

- 2) socio-psychological: the cause of burnout is considered to be the specificity of work itself, which is characterized by a large number of contacts in the "person-to-person" sphere;

- 3) organizational-psychological: the cause of burnout is associated with personality problems in the organizational structure: lack of autonomy and support, role conflicts, inadequate or insufficient feedback from management regarding an individual employee, and others.

The diagnostic tools for identifying the symptoms of professional burnout are widely presented in the psychological and pedagogical literature. Let's name some of the methods that can be used to diagnose this problem: "Diagnosis of the level of emotional burnout" (V.V. Boyko), "Definition of mental burnout" (V.V. Rukavishnikov), "Burnout syndrome in professions of the "person-to-person" system "" (G.S. Nikiforov), "Assessment of one's own potential for "burnout"" (J. Gibson), "Research of the syndrome of "burnout"" (J. Greenberg), "Express diagnosis of the level of psycho-emotional tension (PEN) and its sources " (O.S. Kopina, E.S. Suslova, E.V. Zaikin); "Professional stress test" (T.D. Azarykh, I.M. Tyrtshnikov); "Assessment of the level of social and psychological adaptation of a teacher of a higher school" (modified questionnaire of N.S. Nikiforov); self-actualization questionnaire (SAMOAL); study of sources of social and psychological support (modified questionnaire of V. O. Ananiev); questionnaire "Mental burnout" (N.E. Vodopyanova, O.S. Starchenkova); the author's questionnaire to identify factors that complicate the pedagogical activity of university teachers (I. A. Fomenko); a questionnaire to find out organizational factors of pedagogical activity (I. A. Fomenko) and others [2, 16].

The ability of an individual to effectively perform professional roles is justified by S. Cherniss as the concept of self-efficacy. In his understanding, self-efficacy

reflects an individual's sense of confidence in his ability to control actions that affect his professional life. Among the components of professional self-efficacy, he singled out: professional skill, the ability to maintain friendly relations with others, and the ability to influence the state of affairs within the organization. At the same time, he determines that the ability to set goals and the success of their implementation increase the feeling of self-efficacy. The areas of preservation and strengthening of professional health and prevention of professional burnout of higher school teachers are educational, diagnostic and psychocorrective work, the separate aspects of which are [15]:

- increasing the literacy of teachers on issues of professional efficiency and preservation of professional health;
- provision of organizational and individual conditions in order to prevent professional deformations;
- creation of a comprehensive program of pedagogical support for young teachers with the aim of their adaptation to professional activity, subsequent self-regulation and self-organization of professional actions and self-realization in work, etc.

Psychologists have developed recommendations on ways to overcome professional burnout of an employee. They proposed the following methods of action [5]:

- 1) study one's needs, understand one's goals and imagine the image of one's future, find the meaning of what one does;
- 2) make a transition to a field of activity that is close to the one being performed. This will make it possible to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities (the employee makes a so-called horizontal career);
- 3) without abandoning this type of activity, make it a tool for achieving more global ideas;
- 4) the employee, remaining in the same situation, should focus not on what he knows, knows how to do well, and what he has mastered, but on what is a problem for him. This is how you can find a new meaning in an old profession, and its transformation into a tool for self-development becomes a prevention of burnout.

Stress factors during professional activity can be minimized using the following methods [10]:

- determination of the purpose of the activity;
- establishment of the activity regime;
- planning of the working day;
- improvement of the working space (space-time self-organization);
- delegation of powers;
- observance of executive discipline and work culture, etc.
- formation of activity goals;
- provision of the necessary training, methodical assistance to the employee;
- timely informing about tasks, events related to professional activity and incentives, employee support;
- motivation of employees;
- formation and use of an adequate system of incentives;
- maintaining an optimal social and psychological climate in the team;

- involvement of employees to participate in decision-making on improving the efficiency of activities;
- creation of staff schedules;
- equal distribution of duties and assignments between teachers and others.

An essential factor in the prevention of professional burnout is the training of future professionals in ways of self-organization and organization of professional activities. The initial course "Fundamentals of self-organization in professional activity" is aimed at revealing the internal resources of the individual's activity regarding the analysis and reflection of the situation, circumstances, actions in the future profession and the formation of their ability to optimally choose strategies of functional and role behavior in professional activity [11].

The curriculum includes three modules [13]:

- theoretical aspects of self-organization by a teacher of a higher school of professional and pedagogical activity;
- pedagogical and psychological conditions of effective self-organization by a teacher of professional activity;
- technologies of self-organization in the professional activity of a teacher of a higher school.

The training course program provides for the following methods and types of work: organizational and business games, the role perspective method, project activities, compiling personal and reflective diaries, drawing up professional development plans, training exercises, etc. Thus, prevention of teacher burnout requires the action of a number of organizational, individual and professional factors. One of the conditions for the professional effectiveness of teachers is a comprehensive program aimed at the formation of appropriate motivation, knowledge, skills in organizing and organizing one's own personality, life and professional activities in teachers, which aims to preserve one's health and professional longevity. Nevertheless, the formation of teachers' ability to self-organize their professional activities, which implies their psychological and pedagogical competence regarding the rational organization of work and rest, preservation and restoration of strength and professional efficiency, will contribute to maintaining professional health and mobilizing their efforts in professional activities [14, 19].

In order to establish emotional burnout at the Bukovyna State Medical University, we study the features of the development and prevention of emotional burnout syndrome among teachers of theoretical and practical departments. To diagnose the level of emotional burnout, we use the adapted method of V. V. Boyko, according to which it was established that symptoms of emotional burnout develop in 44% of teachers. In which the presence of psychosomatic and psychovegetative disorders and the development of such symptoms as emotional and moral disorientation, which is manifested by the uncontrolled influence of mood on relationships with others and the development of indifference in communication with colleagues, is noted. There is also the formation of a symptom of the expansion of the sphere of emotion economy, which is characterized by emotional isolation, alienation, the desire to curtail

any communications, and a symptom of the reduction of educational duties, manifested in the desire to spend as little time as possible on the performance of professional duties. To prevent the occurrence of this syndrome, it is possible to use various methods of harmonizing mental and physical health, by influencing the physical and emotional state and influencing thoughts and changing the worldview [17].

We try to follow the general recommendations regarding the correction of physical, mental and spiritual components of health [4, 7]:

I. Recommendations for correction of the physical component.

1. The simplest, universal way to restore personality and the primary need of the human body is an established sleep regime (8 hours). After all, a constant lack of adequate sleep, due to excessive teacher overload, leads to negative acquired habits and stimulates the development of "professional burnout".

2. Diet according to the biological rhythm and the teacher's regimen. Balanced and healthy food is the key to not only physical but also emotional health of a specialist (it is advisable to use useful anti-stress products with a high content of magnesium and vitamin E).

3. Physical activity, namely: sports, morning gymnastics, yoga, fitness, dancing, etc.; massage - will help to restore strength as quickly as possible and will allow to relieve the tension of the whole body.

4. Aromatherapy is a method of therapy using essential oils that are introduced into the body through the respiratory tract (inhalation, inhalation) and through the skin (massage, compress, etc.). This method has a beneficial effect on the human body (smells of citrus fruits, bergamot, spices have a positive effect on the nervous system, there is a feeling of invigoration).

5. Breathing exercises (respiratory gymnastics, bodyflex, etc.) tone the nervous and vascular systems, increase blood circulation, contribute to the formation of the ability to concentrate, eliminate psycho-emotional stress and their consequences.

II. Recommendations for correction of the mental component.

1. Art therapy is a type of psychotherapy and psychological correction based on art and creativity. A special place should be given to "color treatment" isotherapy. The use of green and blue colors promotes relaxation, red and yellow when there is a need to renew energy. Music therapy also contributes to the harmonization of the psycho-emotional state and helps to get rid of negative emotions.

2. Keeping a diary with introspection. It is appropriate to make records of both positive and negative changes and reactions to certain events.

3. Time management consists in planning and correcting the activity schedule for the week. This technique will help the teacher to correctly allocate time for work and rest, without missing anything.

4. Positive psychology is based on positive constructive thinking of the individual, avoiding the use of negative clichés, in order to successfully achieve clearly defined productive goals.

III. Recommendations for correcting the spiritual component.

1. Communicating with family, friends, nature, animals (the environment always helps restore strength and energy).

And although there is no universal recipe for burnout, this problem can still be solved if you deal with it purposefully. It is necessary to separate the work part of life and family life and not to mix them, not to take work home, not to stay too long at work. Useful physical exercises and walks to distract from work. It is also quite useful to take short breaks when you feel that the situation is too stressful.

Conclusion

Modernization of education leads to a higher level of requirements for higher school teachers, whose activities are aimed at creating optimal conditions for revealing and realizing potential opportunities, abilities and needs of students. Professional and high-quality performance of pedagogical activity requires activation of mental processes, concentration of attention, somatic and mental health. Pedagogical activity, due to its oversaturation with stressogenic factors, requires a specialist to have powerful reserves of self-regulation, and that is why it is one of the most emotionally stressful types of work. In this regard, one of the negative consequences of long-term stress is the syndrome of professional burnout. Professional burnout of higher education teachers involves a gradual loss of emotional, cognitive, and physical activity, which is manifested by the corresponding symptoms of exhaustion and fatigue, a decrease in satisfaction from the performance of professional duties, and exacerbation of chronic diseases. The professional destruction of teachers leads to a decrease in the quality indicators of the training of future specialists. Therefore, the specificity of the pedagogical activity of higher school teachers requires effective mobilization of the specialist's internal energy resources, which is impossible without timely detection, prevention and prevention of the phenomenon of professional burnout. The above requires a deeper consideration of the theoretical aspects of the "burnout" syndrome, which will allow developing measures and means of protecting teachers of higher education institutions from the negative impact of psychogenic factors of professional activity.

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